

Rearrangement of N-Chloroanilides in Aqueous Media

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Rates for the rearrangement of N-Chloroacetanilide and its *o*-Chloro derivative in hydrochloric and sulphuric acids increase with increase in acid concentration, however, with change in buffer concentration no appreciable difference of rates has been observed. Constant ionic strength effect data shows that reaction is subject to positive salt effect, involves both acid catalysed and neutral rearrangements and that substitution of chlorine brings no change on the effectiveness of acid catalysis. The sum of calculated acid and neutral rates for rearrangement from ionic strength effect data using second empirical term of Debye-Huckel equation do not agree with experimental rates uniformly over the whole range of acidity. Bunnett and Bunnett-Olsen plot data, Zucker Hammett hypothesis show that reaction is bimolecular and involves a nucleophilic attack of water in rate determining step.

N-CHLOROACETANILIDE undergoes intramolecular rearrangement into *o*- and *p*-chloroacetanilide catalysed by hydrochloric acid in aqueous and non-aqueous media both. Other acids such as sulphuric, perchloric and nitric acids, also catalyse the rearrangement at a slower rate¹⁻⁴. No work appears to have been done on the rearrangement of N-chloroanilides in aqueous acids other than hydrochloric acid and the nature and effectiveness of acid catalysis. The present paper deals with the studies in kinetic of the rearrangement of N-chloroacetanilide and its *o*-chloro derivative in aqueous hydrochloric and sulphuric acids. The impact of *o*-substituted chlorine on the nature and effectiveness of acid catalysis has been found with the help of ionic strength effect data.

Experimental

N-Chloroacetanilide and its *o*-chloro derivative were prepared by the method of Barnes and Porter⁵ and were recrystallized several times from chloroform and light petroleum (40°-60°)

N-Chloroacetanilide m.p. 91°, Expt. %Cl = 20.85, Calcd. %Cl = 20.94.

o-Chloro N-chloroacetanilide m.p. 84°; Expt. %Cl = 34.74; Calcd. %Cl = 34.80.

Rates for the rearrangement of N-chloroanilides (concentration 0.0005M) were followed by taking out aliquots at intervals from reaction mixture immersed in a thermostat, adding potassium iodide and titrating the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate. Good first order rate co-efficients were obtained. Buffer solutions were used for which pH values have been given by Stene⁶. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Results and Discussion

The rates for the rearrangements of N-chloroacetanilide and its *o*-chloro derivative to their nuclear

substituted chloroanilides in aqueous hydrochloric and sulphuric acids increase with increase in acidity. In buffers the change in rates was very slow (Table 1). Such an increase of rates in acids may be due to acid catalysis or ionic acceleration. Rearrangement has been studied at a series of constant ionic strengths in hydrochloric and sulphuric acids and ionic strengths were maintained constant with sodium chloride and sodium sulphate respectively (Table 2). The gradients and intercepts of the lines obtained from plots of rate constants against acid concentration at each ionic strength represent the specific acid catalysed (KH') and specific neutral rates (KN') at that ionic strength respectively. Following conclusions could be drawn from ionic strength effect data:

- (i) an increase of rates with increase in acid concentration at each ionic strength shows that reaction is acid catalysed and these acid catalysed rates are susceptible to ionic strength effect.
- (ii) in the rearrangement of N-chloroacetanilide the lines originate from zero axis indicating that there is no contribution from neutral rates, however, in *o*-chloro derivative neutral rates contribute and are susceptible to ionic strength effect since these lines have different intercepts on rate axis at each ionic strength.
- (iii) gradients of lines show that rearrangement is subject to positive salts effect.

The acid catalysed and neutral rearrangements may be represented as⁷,

$$K_{H^+} = K_{H_0} \exp^b H^+ \mu$$

$$K_N = K_{N_0} \exp^b N \mu$$

where K_{H_0} , K_{N_0} , are specific acid catalysed and specific neutral rates at zero ionic strength, bH^+ and bN are constants in acid and neutral solution

TABLE 1—REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROACETANILIDES AND ITS O-CHLORODERIVATIVES IN AQUEOUS ACIDS

		N-chloroacetanilide												
(M) HCl		0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.8	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	6.0
$10^4 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$		0.08	0.36	0.69	2.36	8.12	22.9	49.6	73.1	75.8	...	...	...	...
**		0.31	0.70	0.22	5.24	6.06	9.7	27.3	67.6	157.9	...	...	...	...
		O-chloro N-chloroacetanilide												
		0.13	...	0.58	1.22	2.59	5.8	6.1	8.3	8.7	9.0	...	11.8	12.7
**		0.89	...	1.37	2.14	2.71	3.6	5.0	7.0	8.3	12.0	...	19.4	33.6
		N-chloroacetanilide												
(M) $\times \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$		0.06	...	0.19	0.39	0.54	0.61	0.86	1.52	2.78	2.94	...	...	...
$10^4 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$		0.04	...	0.13	0.27	0.53	0.77	1.63	3.08	5.43	7.53	...	...	...
		O-chloro N-chloroacetanilide												
		0.07	...	0.10	0.14	0.20	0.25	0.34	0.72	1.33	1.68	2.21	...	...
**		0.01	...	0.04	0.09	0.20	0.32	0.68	1.44	2.50	4.75	7.53	...	...
pH		1.2	1.6	2.2	3.97	4.4	5.2	6.0	7.8					
N-chloro acetanilide		0.08	0.05	0.21	...	0.01	...	0.05	0.56					
O-chloro N-chloro acetanilide		0.16	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.19	0.42					

** Calculated rates :
 N-chloroacetanilide $E = 18.23 \text{ K.Cal/mole}$
 $A = 1.1 \times 10^{11} \text{ sec}^{-1}$
 O-chloro N-chloro acetanilide $E = 14.18 \text{ K.Cal/mole}$
 $A = 1.95 \times 10^8 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
 $\times \text{ at } 40^\circ$
 $\odot \text{ at } 18^\circ$

$\Delta S^\ddagger = -9.77 \text{ e.u.}$
 $\Delta S^\ddagger = -36.3 \text{ e.u.}$

TABLE 2—REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLORO AND ITS O-CHLORODERIVATIVES AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH

N-chloro		o-chloro		N-chloro		o-chloro	
$10^4 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$				$10^6 k \text{ sec}^{-1}$			
$\mu = 0.5$ (M) HCl		$\mu = 1.0$ (M) HCl		$\mu = 0.5$ (M) H_2SO_4		$\mu = 0.5$ (M) H_2SO_4	
0.1 0.48	0.2 0.90	0.1 0.94	0.3 1.51	0.1 4.0	0.2 7.0	0.1 1.7	0.3 5.7
0.4 2.83	0.4 1.94	0.4 2.29	0.5 2.29	0.4 25.0	0.4 8.7		
$\mu = 1.0$	$\mu = 2$	$\mu = 1$	$\mu = 1$				
0.2 1.52	0.2 3.21	0.4 33.0	0.4 13.4				
0.3 3.14	0.5 4.00	0.5 34.0	0.5 13.6				
0.5 5.73	0.9 4.4	0.8 44.0	0.8 26.5				
0.8 10.83	1.0 4.9	...	...				
	1.5 6.4						
$\mu = 2.0$	$\mu = 2.5$	$\mu = 2.0$	$\mu = 2.0$				
0.2 4.1	0.1 1.9	1.5 82.0	1.3 26.5				
0.5 19.9	0.5 3.4	1.6 103.0	1.5 39.3				
0.8 27.7	1.0 5.6	1.9 149.0	1.9 73.1				
1.0 51.1	1.5 7.7	...	...				
1.5 70.4	2.0 7.9	...	...				
$\mu = 2.5$	$\mu = 3.0$						
0.2 5.3	0.5 5.9						
0.5 21.6	1.0 6.8						
1.0 37.6	1.5 7.5						
1.5 87.9	2.0 10.4						
2.0 88.8	...						

and μ is the ionic strength. (The values of K_{Ho} , K_{No} , δN , δH^+ could be obtained as intercepts and gradients from the plots of kH' and kN' against ionic strength). Sum of overall rates via acid catalysed and neutral rearrangements calculated from above equations agree more satisfactorily with experimental rates only in the case of o-chloro-N-chloroacetanilide (Table 1). From K_{Ho} and K_{No} values for N-chloroacetanilide and its o-chloro derivative it appears that effectiveness of acid catalysis is not appreciably effected by substitution of chlorine in ortho position (Table 3). The unit slope obtained from plots of

TABLE 3—SPECIFIC ACID CATALYSED AND NEUTRAL RATES FOR THE REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROACETANILIDES AND ITS O-CHLORODERIVATIVE

		(kH_o)	(kN_o)
N-Chloro	H_2SO_4	2.59	—
	HCl	3.45	—
O-Chloro	H_2SO_4	2.10	—
	HCl	3.28	2.83

TABLE 4—REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROACETANILIDE AND ITS O-CHLORODERIVATIVE

N-chloro (p. cresol) M	0.005	0.01	0.04	0.05	0.08
$10^4 K \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.20	0.99	0.76	0.74	0.52
O-chloro (Phenol) M	0.10	0.20	0.30	...	...
$10^4 K \text{ sec}^{-1}$	117.18	91.70	53.61	...	...

log rates against log CH^+ concentration shows the bimolecular nature of reaction with a nucleophilic attack of water molecule on the basis of Zucker-Hammett hypothesis⁸. Though Zucker-Hammett criteria of mechanism is proved to be quite useful one, Bunnett⁹ suggested a detailed treatment of dependence of acidity function in aqueous solutions. Figure 1 describes the plots of $\log k + \text{H}_0$ and $\log k - \log \text{CH}^+$ against $\log \alpha\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for N-chloroacetanilide and its *o*-chloro derivative and the slopes (ω) indicate the bimolecular nature of reaction with nucleophilic attack of water in the rate determining step. Such observations have also been made in hydrolysis of nitrophenyl¹⁰ and other aryl phosphates¹¹. To get an extra support, Bunnett-Olsen¹² plot data i.e., plots of $\log k + \text{H}_0$ against $\log \text{CH}^+ + \text{H}_0$ for *o*-chloro acetanilide in sulphuric acid (Figure 1) gave slope (ϕ) of 0.36. However, with hydrochloric acid slope (ϕ) of 1.3 instead of < 0.58 suggests that the water molecule is involved as a proton transfer agent in rate determining step, but since the Zucker-Hammett and Bunnett criteria show the bimolecular nature of reaction with nucleophilic attack of water, this has been assigned to be so. The magnitudes of Arrhenius parameters

(Table 1) confirm the bimolecularity of the reaction¹².

In the previous studies on the rearrangement of N-chloroacetanilide catalysed by hydrochloric acid it has been shown that molecular chlorine and acetanilide formed from N-chloro-acetanilide and hydrochloric acid react to give a mixture of *o*- and *p*-chloro-acetanilide. This is not applicable when sulphuric acid is used as catalyst. As evident from above discussion rearrangement is bimolecular with a nucleophilic attack of water. The attack of water molecule takes place on the chlorine of N-chloro anilide with an addition of proton on nitrogen with the formation of hypochlorous acid. Hypochlorous acid thus formed then chlorinates the *o*- and *p*-positions. Few kinetic runs were performed with different concentrations of phenol and rates were found to decrease with increase in concentration of phenol. Since phenols react only with hypochlorous acid, this suggests that the attack of water molecule on the chlorine of N-Cl bond results in the formation of hypochlorous acid. Following mechanism may be formulated on the basis of above results for acid catalysed and neutral rearrangements of N-chloroacetanilides.

FIGURE 1: BUNNETT AND BUNNETT-OLSEN PLOTS FOR THE REARRANGEMENT OF N-CHLOROACETANILIDE AND ITS O-CHLORO DERIVATIVE

$7 + \log k + \text{H}_0$ vs $\log \alpha \text{H}_2\text{O}$	O-CHLORO	● H_2SO_4 , ● HCl
$7 + \log k - \log \text{CH}^+$ vs $\log \alpha \text{H}_2\text{O}$	N-CHLORO	□ H_2SO_4
$7 + \log k + \text{H}_0$ vs $-\log \text{CH}^+ + \text{H}_0$	O-CHLORO	○ HCl
	O-CHLORO	× H_2SO_4 , ● HCl

The final product 2 : 4 dichloroacetanilide was isolated from the rearrangement of *o*-chloro N-chloroacetanilide¹⁴.

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References

1. F. G. SOPER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 1192.
2. F. G. SOPER and D. R. PYRDE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2761.
3. A. R. OLSEN and J. C. HORNELL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1937, 71.
4. R. P. BELL and P. V. DANCKWERTS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1774.
5. BARNES and PORTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1721.
6. S. STENE, *Rec. Trav. Chim., Pay. Bas Belg.*, 1930, 49, 1133.
7. M. M. MEHALA and P. S. BRUJANG, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 1109.
8. L. P. HAMMETT, and L. ZUCKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2791.
9. J. F. BUNNETT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4956.
10. C. A. BUNTON, E. J. FENDLER and F. H. FENDLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 1221.
11. P. W. C. BARNARD, C. A. BUNTON, D. KELLERMAN, M. M. MEHALA, B. L. SILVER, C. A. VERNON and V. A. WELCH, *J. Chem. Soc., Sec. B.*, 1966, 227.
12. J. F. BUNNETT and F. P. OLSEN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, 44, 1917.
13. L. L. SCHALEGAR and F. A. LONG, "Advances in Physical Organic Chemistry", (Ed) V. Gold, Academic Press, London, 1963.
14. M. J. S. DEWAR and J. M. W. SCOTT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1845.